

Public Network-Level Discovery - Using Whois and DNS Probing

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170803> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

When assessing the security of computer systems, web applications are most commonly the target today. However, network based assessments (and thus also attacks) are almost equally important, especially when multiple machines of a particular organization are exposed to the internet. In this article, we will be looking into how to perform the first steps of discovering and probing an organization from a network perspective.

3. Discovering Domain and Hosts

Usually, one would start off either with an IP address range (ex. 192.0.2.0/24) or a domain name (ex. example.com). Our goal is to obtain an IP range as complete as possible for a given organization and the name of their servers (including the domain name). This is where the *Domain Name System* (DNS) comes into play. It translates human-readable domains names to corresponding IP addresses, and sometimes vice-versa.

3.1. Whois Records

Assuming that we've been given only the domain name, we will first query the *Whois database* in order to obtain information about the domain, its *registrar* and related *name servers*. A Whois record must be created when a particular domain is registered. Whois data is important because it may sometimes display personal data on persons responsible for IT management in a particular organization, which is very useful for social engineering attacks.

```
$ whois example.com
whois: This information is subject to an
Acceptable Use Policy.
See https://www.nic.ch/terms/aup/

Domain name:
example.com

Holder of domain name:
```

```
Example Holdings Inc.
Jane Doe
101 First Street
New York, NY
United States of America
Contractual Language: English
```

```
Technical contact:
Any Hosting Inc.
Philip Johnson
525 Flower Lane
New York, NY
United States of America
```

```
Registrar:
Network Registrar Corp.
```

```
First registration date:
2001-01-01
```

```
DNSSEC:N
```

```
Name servers:
ns1.net-reg.com
ns2.net-reg.com
```

4. Dig and the Domain Name System

But we would also like to know the IP addresses of the name servers and possibly a web server behind example.com. For this, we consult dig, an invaluable tool for querying DNS records. Dig itself has many options for issuing different DNS queries, but for now, a simple A query will work just fine (although already rather old, *Madboa* [1] has a wonderful introduction into Dig).

```
$ dig example.com A

; <<> DiG 9.10.3-P4-Debian <<> example.com
;; global options: +cmd
;; Got answer:
;; ->>HEADER<<- opcode: QUERY, status:
NOERROR, id: xxxxx
;; flags: qr rd ra; QUERY: 1, ANSWER: 1,
AUTHORITY: 2, ADDITIONAL: 2

;; OPT PSEUDOSECTION:
; EDNS: version: 0, flags:; udp: 4096
;; QUESTION SECTION:
;example.com.                IN      A

;; ANSWER SECTION:
example.com.                 85937  IN     A
192.0.2.1

;; AUTHORITY SECTION:
example.com.                 3137   IN     NS
```

```

ns1.net-reg.com.
example.com.      3137   IN     NS
ns2.net-reg.com.

; ADDITIONAL SECTION:
ns1.net-reg.com.  494   IN     A
192.0.3.53
ns2.net-reg.com.  494   IN     A
192.0.3.52

```

So, based on this, we now know the IP addresses of the web server and the two DNS servers. But let's try to find more information about the organization in question. The MX record will likely give us the names of the organization's mail servers, while the SOA record will tell us the authoritative name server, and the TXT record will sometimes provide information about the Sender Policy Framework (SPF). SPF was designed to curtail e-mail address spoofing, but for us, this tells us what hosts are allowed to send e-mail for the given domain.

Lastly, we'll try to obtain a list of all hosts of this particular domain, using the AXFR record. However, these so-called zone transfers fail most of the time, *for good reasons* [2].

```

$ dig example.com MX +short
10 mail.example.com
$ dig example.com SOA +short
ns1.net-reg.com. net-reg.anyhosting.com.
2017042502 10800 3600 604800 600
$ dig example.com TXT +short
"v=spf1 mx a ip4:192.0.2.0/24
ip4:192.0.3.52/31 ip4:192.0.4.0/24 ~all"
$ dig example.com AXFR +short
; Transfer failed.

```

Now, despite the fact that we were unable to execute a zone transfer, the TXT record was very helpful, because it told us exactly which IP address blocks belong to that domain. We now have all necessary information to assess the security of the individual hosts through various means.

But so-far, we assumed that we already knew the name of the organization's domain. What if we only know a few IP-addresses, such as 192.0.2.0/24? While it can be misleading, the Whois database will again be the first place to look for information. In this case, we managed to glean information on telephone numbers, the internet service provider, and hints towards the domain name. Based on these hints, we can use common search engines or Dig to try to identify the correct domain, and we can continue with the steps outlined earlier in the article.

```

$ whois 192.0.2.0
inetnum:      192.0.2.0 - 192.0.2.255
netname:     EXAMPLE-NET
descr:       Example Inc.
descr:       New York

```

```

country:      US
admin-c:      JD92-RIPE
tech-c:       JD92-RIPE
status:       ASSIGNED PA
mnt-by:       US-UNISOURCE-MNT
created:      2009-05-15T09:20:00Z
last-modified: 2009-06-19T08:42:58Z
source:       RIPE

```

```

person:       Jane Doe
address:      Example Inc.
address:      101 First Street
address:      New York
phone:        +1-(555)-800 10 30
fax-no:       +1-(555)-800 10 03
nic-hdl:      JD92-RIPE
created:      2009-05-10T00:00:00Z
last-modified: 2016-02-01T00:00:00Z
mnt-by:       RIPE-NCC-LOCKED-MNT
source:       RIPE # Filtered

route:        192.0.0.0/8
descr:        Some-ISP NET-REG aggregate
origin:       ASxxxx
mnt-by:       US-UNISOURCE-MNT
created:      2003-02-01T00:00:00Z
last-modified: 2003-02-01T00:00:00Z
source:       RIPE

```

5. Probing Hosts Further

As soon as we have a reasonably complete list of hosts of the target domain, we are able to scan individual hosts for available services and information made available by them. As opposed to querying Whois or DNS, this step is bound to send network traffic to the hosts of the target domain, and you might not want that for fear of being discovered. There are two ways to approach this problem: either you use a search engine such as *Shodan* [3], or you scan the hosts such that your traffic will get lost in all other traffic. The SANS institute has a great introduction into *using Shodan effectively* [4], for those interested. The other option is to use scanning software directly. Common tools that can be used to scan hosts, are *Nmap* [5], *ZMap* [6], and *Masscan* [7].

6. External Links

- [1] <https://www.madboa.com/geek/dig/>
- [2] <https://www.sans.org/reading-room/whitepapers/dns/securing-dns-zone-transfer-868>
- [3] <https://www.shodan.io/>
- [4] <https://pen-testing.sans.org/blog/2015/12/08/effective-shodan-searches>
- [5] <https://nmap.org/>
- [6] <https://zmap.io/>
- [7] <https://github.com/robertdavidgraham/masscan>